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A Classification of Augmented Reality Approaches for Spatial Data Visualization

Kostas Cheliotis*
Laboratory of Cartography,
School of Rural, Surveying
and Geoinformatics
Engineering,
National Technical University
of Athens

Katerina Pastra[¶]
Institute for Language and
Speech Processing,
ATHENA Research Center

Fotis Liarokapis[†]
CYENS - Centre of
Excellence

Athanasia Darra[¶]
Department of Geography
and Regional Planning,
School of Rural, Surveying
and Geoinformatics
Engineering,
National Technical University
of Athens

Margarita Kokla[‡]
Laboratory of Cartography,
School of Rural, Surveying
and Geoinformatics
Engineering,
National Technical University
of Athens

Maria Bezerianou**
Laboratory of Cartography,
School of Rural, Surveying
and Geoinformatics
Engineering,
National Technical University
of Athens

Eleni Tomai[§]
Laboratory of Cartography,
School of Rural, Surveying
and Geoinformatics
Engineering,
National Technical University
of Athens

Marinos Kavouras^{††}
Laboratory of Cartography,
School of Rural, Surveying
and Geoinformatics
Engineering,
National Technical University
of Athens

ABSTRACT

The field of Augmented Reality (AR) has seen a rapid expansion within the past decades, with many sectors nowadays applying AR methodologies for their own particular visualization needs. One field in particular that has adopted AR visualization techniques is the geospatial sciences, as they have identified the inherent spatial nature of AR as particularly applicable for visualizing (geo)spatial relationships in systems of interest. However, while we can find multiple classification schemes for AR applications in AR literature, to our knowledge no such classification exists that focuses specifically on the spatial aspects of AR applications, namely the visualization size, scale, and acknowledgement of and alignment with the user's physical environment. Therefore no AR classification exists that is specifically applicable to the geospatial sciences. In this paper we present an initial classification of AR approaches for spatial data visualization, highlighting the different spatial characteristics that are of particular relevance to the geospatial sciences. We expect that the initial classification presented here will help researchers working with AR visualizations in organizing their application design with regard to its spatial characteristics.

Index Terms: Human-centered computing—Human computer interaction (HCI)—Interaction paradigms—Mixed / augmented reality; Human-centered computing—Visualization—Visualization theory, concepts and paradigms; Human-centered computing—Visualization—Visualization application domains—Geographic visualization;

1 INTRODUCTION

Augmented Reality (AR) is an inherently spatial visualization method. Milgram et al. identify AR as being closer to the Real

Environment on the Reality-Virtuality Continuum [25], with AR essentially overlaying virtual information over views of the real world. Therefore AR is heavily coupled with the spatial characteristics of the physical environment over which it overlays information, as it needs to accurately couple the digital data with its real-world counterpart. AR has seen significant active research within the engineering sector as a novel facilitator for Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). Furthermore, AR research has significantly expanded to other fields as well, particularly due to recent advances enabling AR applications to be developed and run on many commercially available handheld devices such as smartphones and tablets. This availability of AR along with its inherent spatial nature has also sparked interest in the general area of spatial sciences, which have started to examine AR as a potential visualization method, with the geospatial sciences in particular using AR as a visualisation method to enhance maps and present spatial information in greater detail.

This rise in AR research has resulted in significant innovations, both in terms of technologies as well as applications in different fields, resulting in a diverse range of AR applications. Even through a brief review of recent work¹ we can see a wide array of AR applications, with examples approaching spatial aspects in diverse ways. For example, there exist AR approaches investigating visualizations at small (object) size [15], through medium (room) size [35,36], and all the way up to large (building and city) size [31,34]. Similarly, we can see multiple approaches in the way AR applications attempt to identify the physical morphology around the user and project digital information onto it in a robust manner, from using fiducial markers to align the digital and real-world view [19,39], to using techniques such as Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) to track camera movements in relation to the environment [21,22].

As is evident then, the existing diversity of AR research has resulted in many different AR applications, each pushing boundaries into different directions. While this is welcome as it expands the field, at the same time it presents a potential overall problem: we are seeing more and more applications with core differences between them, while still being identified under the term AR. Therefore it becomes obvious that while AR is a descriptor of data presentation methods, at the same time it is a top-level category that encompasses multiple different approaches for said data presentation methods.

*e-mail: cheliotisk@mail.ntua.gr

[†]e-mail: f.liarokapis@cyens.org.cy

[‡]e-mail: mkokla@survey.ntua.gr

[§]e-mail: etomai@mail.ntua.gr

[¶]e-mail: kpastra@athenarc.gr

^{||}e-mail: nancyd@central.ntua.gr

**e-mail: bez@survey.ntua.gr

^{††}e-mail: mkav@survey.ntua.gr

¹As found mainly in the highly relevant outlet 'Proceedings of the International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)' and similar outlets, from 2006 onwards.

Indeed there were calls highlighting the need for a classification method quite early in the rise of AR research [14], noting that a formal framework would be needed in underpinning AR development to avoid confusion in comparing systems and technologies.

Published work since then has presented multiple taxonomies of AR approaches across different categories and classifications, however to our knowledge no classification exists that discusses specifically and extensively the spatial aspects of AR. Barba & Marroquin [3] do offer a detailed overview on Mixed Reality (MR) and its handling of spatial scale, however that work focuses on documenting uses of spatial scale in MR rather than on presenting a classification scheme and furthermore does not include (nor does it aim to) some additional spatial aspects such as visualization scale, acknowledgement of the user’s physical environment, and virtual-physical alignment methods, as discussed later in this work in Section 3. In this paper we present such a classification method, identifying the different aspects of AR that directly relate to its spatial nature.

2 RELEVANT WORK

A review of existing literature identifies several research papers that have put forward classification methods of AR approaches. An early survey of AR approaches [2] presents a comprehensive overview of the field at the time, highlighting the different application fields, techniques, and major limitations. While this survey came quite early in AR research, it nevertheless outlined core issues in the field, some of which are still relevant today (e.g. see-through display vs video overlay, occlusion, alignment issues).

Suomela and Lehtikoinen present a taxonomy of different AR approaches for visualizing location-based information by introducing the Model-View (MV) taxonomy [38]. The MV taxonomy classifies AR approaches by the number of dimensions used to present the virtual model environment (3D, 2D, etc) along with the user view mode (first-person vs third person), resulting in an MV index for each different approach². Lindeman and Noma present a top-level classification scheme for AR applications based on “where the mixing of real and computer-generated stimuli takes place” [20]. Their classification framework extends beyond the most common visual AR approaches, encompassing AR applications that target other senses as well.

Hugues et al. [13] present a functional taxonomy of AR approaches classified by application aim, identifying two major distinct categories of AR: One aimed at augmenting reality by presenting information relevant to a real element, the other aimed at creating a fully artificial environment that does not correspond to a real-world element. Normand et al. [30] present a meta-review of existing AR taxonomies, identifying four main categories of AR classifications (technique-centered, user-centered, information-centered, interaction-centered). They furthermore propose a new taxonomy comprised of three core axes and one optional (degrees of freedom required for tracking, visualization mode, temporal base of content, and optionally the rendering modality).

A taxonomy of visualization methods for linking digital information with real-world objects is presented by Müller et al. [28], focusing specifically on the different methods for communicating the spatial relationship between virtual and real. A more comprehensive AR visualization taxonomy is presented by Zollmann et al. [45], aiming at providing AR researchers and developers without extensive technical background the necessary information to apply AR visualization techniques. Their AR visualization taxonomy identifies six distinct reoccurring axes: visualization purpose, virtual data visibility, virtual cues, data filtering, visual abstraction, and compositing.

²For example, a 3D environmental model with a first person view would be classified as MV(3,1)

All of the above classification systems present valid approaches for categorizing AR applications in some regard, however none of them presents a comprehensive outline of the spatial characteristics of AR. Additionally some of the classifications do not even include the spatial parameters explicitly but rather acknowledge them implicitly, through the spatial nature of AR application, and therefore are of limited relevance for geospatial visualizations. Furthermore, to our knowledge no classification exists that fully addresses the spatial nature of AR. As such in the following section we present a classification system for AR applications that categorizes AR approaches across multiple inherently spatial axes.

3 CLASSIFICATION AXES

We present here four classification axes of AR regarding its spatial aspects. The four axes we have identified are: the *visualization size* that relates to the extents of the visualization itself; the *visualization scale* that relates to how much larger or smaller the presented virtual data is in relation to the real world system that it is describing; the level of *acknowledgement of the user’s physical environment* that relates to whether the AR application takes into account the morphology of the physical environment within which it is deployed; and finally the *view alignment methods* that relate to how the AR application attempts to align the virtual objects with the physical environment around them. The classification presented here has been designed with a particular focus on spatial data visualization.

3.1 Visualization Size

The first spatial axis for classifying AR visualizations is the *visualization size*, which relates to the extents of the visualization itself, or in other words how large of an area/volume the digital view occupies. We identify three categories: visualizations *smaller than human size*, visualizations *at human size*, and visualizations *larger than human size*. This classification has long been discussed in geographic and cognitive sciences as the different spatial scales as perceived by humans, first introduced by Montello [26], and elaborated further specifically on its relation with AR by Barba & Marroquin [3].

Figure 1: Visualization Size

More specifically, small visualizations (Figure 1a) take place in what Montello calls “figural” space, where the entirety of a virtual object can be perceived from a single point of view, without requiring a change in either angle of view or position. Changes in point of view might provide new information, but nonetheless the entirety of the virtual object can be perceived from a single point of view. Examples of this category are found in 3D object reconstruction [44] and in paper map enhancement via AR [1].

Visualizations at human size (Figure 1b) take place in a space that is slightly larger than human size but can be perceived from

a single location, and match what Montello calls "vista" space; such visualizations do not require a change in position to experience the virtual world, but do require a change in camera orientation, i.e. the user needs to rotate the camera around to fully perceive the visualization. Such approaches in AR are often found to take place in a single room, as demonstrated in recent examples [36,41].

Larger than human size visualizations (Figure 1c) take place in Montello's "environmental" space, where the visualization is significantly larger than human size, and require a change in both position and orientation to fully apprehend the visualization in its entirety. In geospatial fields such visualizations are often found to span the size of large buildings or the urban environment. Examples of such approaches are found in work focusing on effective movement methods in wide area virtual environments [34], wayfinding and navigation [29], and urban AR approaches [17,31].

3.2 Visualization Scale

The second spatial axis is that of the *visualization scale*, which relates to the size of the presented data *in relation to the size of the real-world element they represent*. The concept of scale is integral part of cartographic sciences, and indeed any field whose focus is on significantly large systems. Multiple meanings of scale can be found in geography [27], however it is the concept of 'Cartographic scale' that is used most often and is of interest here. The concept of cartographic scale relates to the ratio of the representation's size to the actual size of the element it represents and is often expressed in fractions³.

Figure 2: Visualization Scale

AR visualizations presented at the same scale (Figure 2b) are at a 1:1 scale to the source, meaning they are presented without size change to the viewer. Instances of this category are found for example in 3D object reconstruction [44] where the reconstructed object is presented overlaid over the source (real-world) object, and urban AR approaches [17,31] where data about the urban environment is overlaid over the urban environment itself.

Visualizations presented at small scale (Figure 2c) are presented to the viewer at a reduced size and are said to be scaled-down representations, for example at a scale ratio of 1:100, where the virtual representation is 100 times smaller than the source. Such representations are among the most used in the geospatial sciences, whose system focus is already examined at scale. Instances of this category are most evident in cartographic AR applications, for example in AR paper map enhancement [1] and collaborative geospatial analytics systems [23].

³e.g. '1:100', where one real-world unit is equivalent to 100 representation units, or in other words the representation is 100 times smaller than the real-world element.

The third category of visualizations presented at large scale (Figure 2d) is rarely found in geospatial sciences, but is included here nonetheless for completeness. In these cases, the element of interest is presented at an enlarged size, i.e. scaled-up, for example at a scale ratio of 100:1, where the virtual representation is 100 times larger than the source. Such visualizations are often found in fields whose focus is on micro-systems and the inner workings and inter-relations are not evident to the human eye, with notable examples of this category found for example in AR applications for biology [10,12].

3.3 Acknowledgement of User Physical Environment

The third spatial axis relates to how the AR application *acknowledges the user's physical environment* in the real world. This aspect is relevant in multiple instances for AR applications, with application found predominantly for rendering purposes, i.e. to accurately render a virtual object so that its superimposition over the view of the real world is closer to what the user would see if the object actually existed in the real world. In other words this aspect relates to how the virtual world is set to *respond* to real-world conditions, and is most notably encountered in matters of occlusion (where real objects must obscure part of the virtual object) and reflection (where virtual reflective surfaces reflect the real-world environment). Figure 3 provides a schematic demonstration of the different approaches for occlusion purposes.

Figure 3: Acknowledgement of physical environment for occlusion

The first category of environment acknowledgement is that of *no acknowledgement* at all, where the virtual scene has no information about the real-world environment within which it is placed. Instances in this category are often found in earlier AR approaches where robust tracking is the main focus [4,11]. As the AR application has no information about the real-world environment, this is disregarded for all rendering matters, with virtual objects often being rendered over the physical environment even in cases where the viewer would have expected them to be occluded by a physical object (Figure 3a).

The second category is that of *pre-computed environments*, where the physical properties of the environment are available to the AR application beforehand, and the application can retrieve this information during runtime to have virtual objects respond as needed and provide a more 'real'-like and blended view between virtual and real. In occlusion scenarios this results in virtual objects being occluded by real-world objects that are 'in-front' of them (Figure 3b), and is often achieved by developing a 3D model of the physical environment beforehand [9]. In scenarios involving reflection this is achieved by capturing light conditions in the environment beforehand in high dynamic range (HDR) to produce an HDR map [16],

which is then available during runtime so that virtual objects can appear to respond to light conditions in the real world. The main advantage of pre-computed environment data is the fact that developers can spend considerable time or computational power beforehand to produce high fidelity representations as needed, and therefore having a more detailed representation of the physical environment during runtime. At the same time however their pre-computed nature presents them with a distinct drawback, in that such approaches cannot respond to changes in the environment during runtime.

The third category identified here is that of *generating environments in real-time*, i.e. while the AR application is running. In these instances, the AR application employs algorithms during runtime to recognize and generate the environment on the spot, either in terms of generating virtual 3D meshes of real-world objects [33], or for capturing light conditions to use for reflections [41]. For occlusion purposes (Figure 3c), real-time generation methods are able to detect real world objects in front of virtual objects and occlude accordingly during runtime [8, 40]. Due to their real-time nature, approaches in this category provide the opposite advantages and disadvantages to the pre-computed approaches: they are able to respond to changes in the real-world environment during runtime, however at the same time they may produce environments at lower fidelity compared to pre-computed maps, as they need to produce results within a limited time to maintain smooth performance, potentially at the cost of fidelity.

3.4 View Alignment Methods

The fourth spatial axis focuses on how AR applications attempt to align the view of the virtual environment with that of the physical environment. Through a cursory examination, this category appears to be tightly related to the third axis (acknowledgement of user's physical environment). However this axis differs on one significant aspect: while the acknowledgement of the physical environment is primarily concerned with matters of *immersion* (how to best identify morphological characteristics for occlusion or reflection purposes), the view alignment axis is concerned with matters of *meaningful placement*, i.e. correctly identifying the *place* where the AR application is running in, so that it can present to the user meaningful information about the objects around them. Due to this distinct difference, we identify this fourth axis which focuses on how AR applications essentially identify where they are in a particular space.

3.4.1 No Alignment

In the first category of view alignment methods, AR applications *do not align* in any meaningful way the virtual with the physical space. This approach is most often found in initial 'Hello World' implementations of AR frameworks, and its application is limited to only inspecting a 3D model from various angles. Applications in this category often initialize a virtual environment using the device position and orientation at application start time, and subsequently make use of delta transformations (frame-by-frame differences) to track device movement and convert it into movement of the virtual camera around the virtual object.

3.4.2 Alignment via Markers

The second category of view alignment methods includes AR applications that make use of *fiducial markers* to align the virtual with the physical environment. Markers in this context constitute some predetermined object that exists in the real world and which the AR application has been configured to identify via its imaging sensor (e.g. camera) in some form. With this setup, when the AR application identifies the physical marker as being in view, it can calculate the angle of view and distance of the device in relation of the marker, and thus achieve alignment between the physical and virtual views. Markers are found in two categories: *2D markers*, predetermined flat images often with sharp contrasts and significant features [7, 18],

and *3D markers*, pre-scanned 3D objects of well-defined physical morphology with unique significant features [37, 42].

3.4.3 Alignment via Physical Morphology

The third category contains methods that align the virtual and physical environment by identifying unique morphological features in the physical environment around the user as captured by the AR device's imaging sensor, and subsequently tracking the change in position and orientation of the device relative to the identified features frame-by-frame. This process of generating a virtual representation of the environment map and subsequently using it to track the device orientation in it is known as 'Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping (SLAM)', and applications of it are shown to be able to match real and virtual orientation and view alignment continuously and consistently [5, 32, 43].

3.4.4 Alignment via Geolocation

The fourth category of view alignment contains approaches that make use of a device's geolocation sensors to match virtual with physical space. In these cases, an AR application running on a handheld device can make use of the device's GPS sensor to first of all place the virtual environment at a particular location on the Earth's surface, and subsequently utilize inertial and other sensors (accelerometer, compass, etc) to track the device's movement in space [6, 24]. Approaches relying solely on GPS and inertial sensors might suffer from reduced accuracy when aligning virtual and physical views compared to other (marker-based or markerless/SLAM) approaches, however they have the benefit of being able to be deployed potentially anywhere on Earth.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Classification Completeness

The AR spatial properties classification scheme presented here constitutes an initial and preliminary proposal for a classification scheme with a focus on AR applications in the geospatial sciences. As such we expect that it might require revisions in the future in response to advances in the field and due to more robust and detailed study. However even within this context, we identify that some of the classification work presented here is (nearly) complete. We consider two of the axes to have been fully defined in terms of category range, one to have been mostly defined, and one to still be open-ended.

More specifically, the first two axes (visualization size and scale) relate to spatial properties that have been extensively studied and discussed in other fields (particularly geography and cognitive psychology) and have already been defined within the scope of those fields, and are therefore considered to be fully defined in range. While the number of categories in these two axes might need to be revised in the future in response to new technologies and user needs, we expect that the *range* of available options is fully contained by the categories presented in each axis (in relation to human size or scale, with one category smaller, one larger, and one for similar). Somewhat similarly for the third axis (acknowledgement of physical environment), we expect that the categories presented here encompass the full extent of potential options (one category for pre-computed approaches, one for real-time, and one for the absence of approaches), and as such while these broad categories might need to be broken down further into sub-categories, we do not expect new approaches to fall outside the scope of the proposed categories. Nevertheless, given that this axis is predominantly driven by technological advances and is not tightly related to other fields, we consider this classification axis to be mostly (but not fully) defined in range. The final axis (view alignment methods) is the one mostly driven by technological innovation and as such we identify that significant changes might need to be introduced at a later time, therefore we consider this classification axis to still be open-ended.

4.2 Combinations of Axes

The classification axes presented in this paper are considered independent of each other, meaning that AR applications can be described by any combination of axis categories, without significant limitations between axes. For example, work presented in both [44] and [1] is smaller than human size in terms of visualization size, however [44] presents virtual objects in 1:1 scale while [1] presents virtual objects in small scale. At the same time, while both [44] and [31] present virtual objects at 1:1 scale, the former is presented in smaller than human size, the latter at larger than human size.

While the classification axes presented here are more or less independent of one another, some combinations are inherently incompatible or illogical, dependent on target data. For example, a visualization of a spatially large data set (e.g. urban systems) will most likely be presented either at the same (1:1) or small scale (1:100) but rarely at a large scale (100:1), as the spatial relationships are already quite larger than the immediate human perception and scaling them up would make their perception more difficult. Furthermore, the visualisation scale will dictate the visualisation size in this case: a spatially large data set presented in normal scale will need to be able to span an area larger than human size (e.g. visualising air pollution at street level, where the user needs to visit different locations to see air quality at each location), whereas a large data set scaled down will most likely be presented at smaller than human size, to present an overview of the data set. On the other hand, a large data set in 1:1 scale presented at a smaller than human size (i.e. presented on a desk top) is illogical, as that would present a very narrow and unusable view of the data.

Similarly, a spatially small data set (e.g. micro- or nano-engineering projects) will most likely be presented in large scale (100:1) to magnify details imperceptible to the human eye, as other visualisation scales would render these details even more imperceptible to the human eye. Furthermore, it will most likely be presented at a visualisation size smaller than or at human (room) scale, as at this size all relevant details can be perceived within a single view or with minor rotation. In a similar fashion, acknowledgement of the user's physical environment in terms of occlusion can be fully disregarded or made an integral part of the visualization, depending on visualization goals. For example, physical environment occlusion can be disregarded if the aim of an AR visualization is to provide a detailed view of some complex machinery in a scaled up view, as physical boundaries would only get in the way of the visualisation. On the other hand, an indoor navigation and wayfinding AR system would need to take into account the user's physical surroundings at all times, to indicate visually and with increased clarity the directions in relation to the user's environment.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The classification scheme presented in this paper aims to help researchers and practitioners of AR visualizations in organizing their application design during the conceptualization stage with regard to its spatial characteristics, i.e. aid developers to clarify the AR development needs with regard to the goal of the app. The classification presented here has been developed mainly for use in geospatial sciences research, however it is expected that AR developers in general will benefit from this classification scheme, as it highlights core aspects of AR, encountered in most AR applications. This classification scheme is at an early stage, and contains categorizations specifically relevant for developing AR applications within the field of geospatial sciences. While these classification axes are useful for geospatial AR applications, they are not considered exhaustive, and we anticipate that this work can be expanded further, in multiple directions. We have already discussed the possibility of future technological advances introducing new methods for aligning virtual and real environments. Additionally, this classification scheme focused on *spatial* data visualization, however we identify the potential for

an AR classification scheme for data visualization in general, encompassing aspects such as the temporal dimension of data and the real vs. abstract nature of the phenomena being visualized. In the future, we aim to expand the classification scheme to include elements of data visualization as mentioned here, as well as updating the scheme as needed when new methodologies emerge.

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